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ABSTRACT

The present research focuses on study of diversity of pond aquatic macrophytes of Sindhiya Nagar Durg district C.G. Survey work with respect to seasonal influence was conducted during the period December 2023 to November 2024 focusing on importance and conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem. Survey work includes collection, identification, observation and documentation of data. The data revealed the presence of diversified pond aquatic macrophytes consisting of 17 species, 13 families and 5 life forms including submerged, free-floating, rooted floating, emergent and surface aquatic macrophytes. During winter, summer and rainy season the maximum abundance of submerged aquatic macrophytes were recorded followed by free floating and the least dominant life forms were rooted, emergent and surface macrophytes.

KEYWORDS: Biodiversity, Macrophytes, Submerged, species, Life forms, ecosystem.**1. INTRODUCTION**

Sindhiya Nagar is a part of Durg district in Chhattisgarh. Durg is known for its industrial areas including Bhilai steel plant. Sindhiya Nagar is a sub locality in Katulbod, durg district, Chhattisgarh, India. There is also a Hanuman temple in Durg. Durg district was formed in 1906 from parts of Raipur and Bilaspur district. The aquatic plants growing near the water bodies which provide tremendous environmental benefits and play crucial role in sustainable development, management and assessment of the coastal lakes are known as Macrophytes.(Fareed, Haroon & Rabeh, 2008)¹⁰. The Numerous factors like topography, wind velocity, water turbidity and depth, are responsible for controlling the diversity and distribution of these aquatic macrophytes.

A specific type of substrate is required for the growth of macrophytes which further provides a unique habitat for other organisms. They are predominantly found in areas with upwelling ground water and can grow in a mixture of sand, muck thereby promoting particle sedimentation, modification of the microclimate and prevent water from mixing by creating thermal gradient. Moreover they are important source of nutrient incorporating nutrient from the anoxic sediments and then releasing them in to the water column up to senescence which are largely retained by plants until they decay. Furthermore Macrophytes provide important habitat for organisms such as bacteria, zooplanktons, invertebrates, fishes, amphibians as well as they are major source of food for many invertebrates and vertebrates(Peter and Lodge, 2009)¹³. The most productive communities in the world are generally emergent macrophytes which are most common in lentic ecotones. Different part of the aquatic plants provides shelter and substrate to numerous aquatic organisms, play important role in recycling of nutrients and removal of pollutants. They are persistent pollutant and bear toxic removal capacity and thus included in constructed wetland technology (Saloni sachdeva, 2023)¹¹. Macrophytes are responsible for differential productivity and morphological changes, filtration, erosion, stabilizing of surface, insulation and enhancement of micro-organisms. (Brix1994)¹².

Streams and rivers are having great ecological as well as economic importance. The beginning of Lotic ecology was from Europe focusing on the distribution, abundance and taxonomic composition of aquatic organisms and in North American with a focus on fishery biology. The fishery biologists and terrestrial plant ecologists are highly involved in interdisciplinary stream river researches since 1980. The lotic biota like algae, macrophytes, benthic invertebrates and fishes have evolved adaptations to their running water setting. The most important limiting factor for occurrence of macrophytes in running waters is light and current. There are three ecological categories of macrophytes which includes those that are attached to substrate like mosses and liverworts, rooted in the substrate like submerged plants of Hydrocharitaceae, Ceratophyllaceae and emergent (Potamogetonaceae, Ranunculaceae, Cruciferae and free floating substrate like Lemnaceae and Pontederiaceae. (Wilzbach and Cummins, 2008)⁹. Therefore studies on aquatic macrophytes found in various ponds or water bodies have become increasingly important because these plants have an impact on functional values of wetlands. (Deorao and Sarang, 2024)⁷. Looking to the tremendous benefits and ecological roles of Pond aquatic macrophytes, understanding of the wetland biodiversity is also very important.

Biological diversity is the variability among living organisms from all sources including terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems. They are a part of ecological complexes which includes diversity within species, between species, and of ecosystems (Sharma and Saraf, 2016)¹⁴. Biodiversity is a vast array of all plants, animals, insects and micro-organisms inhabiting the earth either in aquatic or terrestrial habitats. The human civilization greatly depend upon this biodiversity for their basic needs of survival like food, fodder, fuel, fibre, fertilizer, timber, rubber, leather, medicines and several raw materials. This Diversity is important for the long term sustainability of the environment as well as for continuity of life on earth. But due to habitat degradation, loss of wild stock in association with loss of local traditional Knowledge led to rapid degradation of biological resources all over the globe. Hence the conservation as well as understanding of biodiversity is crucial. Hence the role and importance of rich diversity of aquatic macrophytes cannot be ignored and required a wide study for further research and since there are only limited literatures are available on study of pond aquatic macrophytes, therefore the present investigation deals with the study of diversity of pond aquatic macrophytes in Sindhiya Nagar District Durg C.G.

2. STUDY AREA

The study area was Sindhiya Nagar Durg C.G near Railway station surrounded by temples and religious places and there is a pond in the centre. Temples include Shitala temple and Hanuman temple. It is a religious place for many peoples and attracts tourists also. The study area includes rich diversity of macrophytes. Since they play very important role in nutrient recycling, removal of toxic pollutants from the water bodies thereby playing a very crucial role in the ecosystem. Therefore understanding the diversity of aquatic macrophytes and hence conservation of their biodiversity is important.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The present research work was conducted during the year December 2023 to Nov. 2024 during winter, summer and rainy season. Both qualitative and quantitative analysis of aquatic pond macrophytes was performed following the standard protocol of (Biswas & Calder 1984¹, Mishra, 1974⁴ and Deoraw & Sarang 2024⁷). During the research work, the aquatic macrophytes, specimens were collected, identified based on life forms and comparative study of seasonal influence regarding the availability of aquatic macrophytes were performed and data was recorded which was listed below in the table.

Seasonal survey was conducted in the current study in 2023 to 2024 during winter, summer and rainy season. Qualitative and quantitative analysis as well as specimen identification was performed using the standard method of (Biswas & Calder 1984¹, Mishra 1974⁴ and Deoraw and Sarang 2024⁷).

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The study of the pond aquatic Macrophytes in Sindhiya Nagar Durg district revealed the presence of Heterogenous collection of seventeen species, thirteen families and five life forms. Thirteen families include two families each of Pontederiaceae, Hydrocharitaceae, Potamogetonaceae and Lythraceae. And one family each of Salviniaceae, Cabomaceae, Characeae, Convulvulaceae, Lemnaceae, Marsiliaceae, Nelumbonaceae, Polygonaceae and Araceae. Out of the five life forms found, ten forms belong to submerged macrophytes, four are free floating macrophytes, and remaining three are rooted floating, emergent and Surface macrophytes.

Maximum dominating macrophytes were found to be submerged macrophytes followed by free floating and the least dominating life forms were rooted, emergent and surface aquatic macrophytes. The comparative study and the effect of seasonal influence on the diversity of aquatic macrophytes were observed with respect to winter, summer and rainy season in which the data showed the maximum abundance of ten, ten and six submerged macrophytes respectively in winter, summer and rainy season. Whereas total of four, four, and three free floating macrophytes were observed during winter, summer and rainy season respectively. Rooted, emergent and surface aquatic macrophytes were the least dominating macrophytes in each of the above three seasons.

Table 1: Aquatic macrophytes found in Sindhiya Nagar Durg pond

S.N.	Macrophytes	Family	Life form	Season (Dec. 2023 to Nov. 2024)		
				Winter	Summer	Rainy
1.	<i>Azolla caroliniana</i>	Salviniaceae	Free floating	+	+	-
2.	<i>Eichornia crassipes</i>	Pontederiaceae	Free floating	+	+	+
3.	<i>Lemna perpusilla</i>	Lemnaceae	Free floating	+	+	+
4.	<i>Pistia (Water cabbages)</i>	Araceae	Free floating	+	+	+
5.	<i>Cabomba caroliniana</i>	Cabombaceae	Submerged	+	+	-
6.	<i>Chara globularis (Musk grass)</i>	Characeae	Submerged	+	+	-
7.	<i>Hydrilla verticillata</i>	Hydrocharitaceae	Submerged	+	+	+
8.	<i>Marsilea villosa</i>	Marsileaceae	Submerged	+	+	-
9.	<i>Najas minor</i>	Hydrocharitaceae	Submerged	+	+	+
10.	<i>Neluncdo nucifera (Lotus)</i>	Nelumbonaceae	Submerged	+	+	+
11.	<i>Persicaria hydropiperoides</i>	Polygonaceae	Submerged	+	+	+
12.	<i>Potamogeton crispus</i>	Potamogetonaceae	Submerged	+	+	+
13.	<i>Potamogeton gramineus</i>	Potamogetonaceae	Submerged	+	+	+
14.	<i>Trapa natans</i>	Lythraceae	Submerged	+	+	-
15.	<i>Water hyacinth</i>	Potederiaceae	Surface	+	+	-
16.	<i>Rotala rotundifolia</i>	Lythraceae	Emergent	+	+	+
17.	<i>Ipomoea aquatic</i>	Convolvulaceae	Rooted floating	+	+	+

Fig. No. 01 : Comparative study of pond aquatic macrophytes in Sindhiya Nagar Durg

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The study of aquatic macrophytes is crucial because they play a vital role in maintaining healthy Aquatic ecosystems by regulating nutrient cycles, providing food and shelter for various aquatic organisms, indicating water quality and contributing to overall biodiversity, making them a key indicator of ecosystem health and a valuable tool for environmental monitoring and management strategies. In the present study submerged aquatic macrophytes were abundantly present life forms. Submerged macrophytes play an important role in the structuring and functioning of aquatic freshwater systems. (Carpenter and Lodge, 1986²; Jeppesen *et al.*, 1998⁸). The study and Knowledge of pond ecology play a very important role for physiological data of aquatic macrophytes irrespective of any fresh water bodies. (Deorao and Sarang, 2024)⁷. Various researches on aquatic macrophytes diversity were performed by many ecologists. (Cowardin *et al.*, 1979¹⁶; Keddy, 2000¹⁵). Habitat loss is a challenge for all species. Overexploitation from extractive uses such as commercial fishing and game hunting and other human and animal activities can greatly reduce species number leading to extinction. (Alison and Monika, 2002)⁵. Thus Biodiversity conservation efforts are essential in maintaining functioning ecosystems, a steady food supply, spiritual purposes, for daily household activities, water quality management and ecological studies.

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